

CHOICE OF TREATMENT METHODS FOR GASTRASHYSIS AND OMPHALOCELE IN INFANTS

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ABSTRACT

In babies, omphalocele and gastroschisis are considered severe congenital defects of the anterior abdominal wall, occurring in 1.6-3.2% of all other congenital anomalies. If not treated in time, the mortality rate can reach 100%.

There is no single universally accepted method of treatment of these developmental defects. "There are especially big differences in the approaches to the treatment of large and giant omphaloceles and total gastroschisis, and cases with a strong viscero-abdominal disproportion limit performing radical plastic surgery of the anterior abdominal wall using local tissue." A significant share of unsatisfactory results, the lack of optimal treatment method, taking into account the size of the defect of the anterior abdominal wall and the clinical course of the disease, the choice of the first aid type, indicate the urgency of continuing research in this direction

Relevance of the problem. In babies, omphalocele and gastroschisis are considered severe congenital defects of the anterior abdominal wall, occurring in 1.6-3.2% of all other congenital anomalies. If not treated in time, the mortality rate can reach 100%. There is no single universally accepted method of treatment of these developmental defects. "There are especially big differences in the approaches to the treatment of large and giant omphaloceles and total gastroschisis, and cases with a strong viscero-abdominal disproportion limit performing radical plastic surgery of the anterior abdominal wall using local tissue." A significant share of unsatisfactory results, the lack of optimal treatment method, taking into account the size of the defect of the anterior abdominal wall and the clinical course of the disease, the choice of the first aid type, indicate the urgency of continuing research in this direction.

Purpose: selection of treatment methods for gastroschisis and omphalocele in infants.

Materials and methods: studies were conducted in 2006-2022 in 243 babies at the Republican Neonatal Surgery Educational-Treatment-Methodological Center. Of these, 133 (54.7%) had omphalocele, 110 (45.3%) had gastroschisis. Out of 133 (54.7%) babies born with the diagnosis of omphalocele, 78 (58.6%) were boys, 55 (41.4%) were girls. Out of 110 (45.3%) babies born with gastroschisis, 62 (56.4%) were boys and 48 (43.6%) were girls. When all patients came to the clinic, in addition to the general clinical examination methods, general radiography of the abdomen, ultrasound examination of internal organs and anterior abdominal wall defects, echocardiography, and neurosonography were performed.

Results: Of 243 infants with gastroschisis and omphalocele, 221 (91%) underwent operative treatment: 181 (82%) underwent radical operative treatment, and 40 (18%) underwent staged surgical treatment. Preoperative preparation consisted of correction of homeostasis disorders and it was 6-24 hours. 22 (9%) patients underwent conservative treatment. The reason for conservative treatment was that they had many additional defects that prevented surgery. Preoperative preparation consisted of correction of homeostasis disorders and it was 6-24 hours. All infants with omphalocele underwent decompression of the gastrointestinal tract and protection of the hernia sac with sterile dry rubber gloves. The criterion of effectiveness of pre-operative preparation was assessed by recovery of diuresis and hemodynamic indicators.

Conclusion: in gastroschisis and omphalocele, the smaller the size of the anterior abdominal wall defect is an indication for radical plasticity of the anterior abdominal wall, it is advisable to perform a staged operation in large-sized types..

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